

A Study on Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Cloud Kitchen with Special Reference to Coimbatore

Alen Denis A¹, Dr Geetha R²

¹III B Com CA, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

²Associate Professor & Head, Department of B Com CA, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Abstract:

Cloud Kitchen is a food service establishment that does not have a physical dining area for customers. It wholly relies on digital or online services for accepting orders. This food service has increased rapidly due to increased technological changes, lifestyle changes, and growing demands for food services due to factors such as the Covid-19 pandemic. This research study aims at exploring consumer buying behaviour towards Cloud Kitchen food services in Coimbatore, with particular emphasis on consumer awareness, consumer satisfactions, and other factors that may influence consumer buying behaviour. For conducting research, the study used the descriptive research method, relying on primary and secondary research. For primary research, a sample of 100 participants was selected through convenience sampling. For secondary research, existing research articles, journals, magazines, and other online sources were used. From the research findings, it was identified that the consumer is mostly young adults, educated, and comes from nuclear families. Relatives, friends, and advertisements are key areas for generating consumer awareness about Cloud Kitchen services. From the research study, it is concluded that consumer satisfactions are mostly driven by ratings or reviews, packaging, and hygiene. Hence, food quality is very vital for Cloud Kitchen food services.

Keywords: Cloud kitchen, Food delivery, Marketing strategy, Hygiene, Online platforms, Purchasing decisions, Feedback

Introduction:

Rapid technological advancements have resulted in a significant effect on marketing practices in the past years. Along with advancements in technology, the needs and behaviour of customers have changed as well. New products are being showcased in the market every day, and customers are constantly being advertised through television, radio, web links, and social media. This advertising process takes place specifically to target customers. Despite all the focus being on activities such as purchasing and production, marketing plays an equally significant part in connecting all this to customers. Marketing can be likened to a system which holds everything together pertaining to different business areas. Whereas finance is engaged in managing money and manufacturing is involved in product production, another area that is managed is customers through which the product is marketed. Earlier, marketing essentially involved advertising and sales. In current circumstances, it has been employed in understanding customer needs, developing an image for brands, and helping in business decisions. To establish a successful business, it has become imperative to acquire

customers as well as retain them in the market. Such retention has become possible to a large extent by adopting appropriate marketing channels. Marketing professionals are required to understand how customers react to a business entity's image in the market. A marketing strategy acts as a guiding tool for business goals and objectives. The process involves determining the organizational mission and goals followed by allocating business units their respective roles and resources. Market evaluation is periodically conducted to assess business strategies and change them for better results and performance. Marketing research helps these activities by providing necessary information to the decision-maker and has a very definite role to play in the marketing process. Marketing research includes problem-oriented data collection and data analysis. Such information helps the manager to comprehend the market situation with a view to propose relevant action. Market research is always related to a specific target market, whereas marketing research may relate to many areas like distribution, effectiveness of advertising, and efficiency of sales force. Thus, market research is only a part of marketing research. The steps of research procedure

which may be generally followed are: problem specification, data collection, analysis of findings, and drawing of conclusion.

Review of Literature:

Dr. Deepali & K. J. Somaiya (2024)¹, as a matter of fact, also emphasizes in this study the “Opportunities and Challenges for cloud kitchen owners” Today; all online business activity is performed in a closed network all over the world. Only those persons or devices who have been accredited get a chance to enter a closed network. This system provides a controlled environment for communication. This mechanism is used for protecting all critical information. For example, patient information. Restaurants, with the assistance of food delivery online sites such as Swiggy or Zomato, get new customers. This also provides them with the easy access option. However, restaurants get charged a commission for each delivered meal. This might appear little, but it could create some problems regarding profits, data rights, or commissions. These online sites value medical records in a hospital or also banking.

Rafiuddin Ahmed & Maria Sultana (2024)² “Investigating the factors that drive the success of cloud kitchen in Bangladesh” This comes because, as a result of people’s growing apprehension about dining out, forced lockdowns and social distancing policies have brought about a vast and rapid growth in online food delivery services. Cloud Kitchens, focusing on cleanliness and contactless delivery, also gained popularity in this context. Cloud Kitchens, a fairly new yet growing idea, also has a large potential market in Bangladesh, though a cloud kitchen system is a worldwide rival to conventional restaurants. A number of factors, including psychological, social, economic, and personal dimensions, influence purchasing decisions regarding a product or a service. Consumers assess the value of a service or product in relation to a fixed cost. A reasonable price attracts clients, but charging an unreasonable price repels them away.

Mr. Donald James & Dr. Anil Kumar (2023)³ in this study, the emerging theme is “The Evaluate customer awareness of cloud kitchen in Mangalore city” which was specifically focused to evaluate the

awareness of cloud kitchen and to compare the services of the cloud kitchen with other food joints. The study was conducted by utilizing both primary as well as secondary sources of data. The questionnaire was administered to collect responses from a sample size of 70 respondents. The techniques adopted in analysing the obtained information are Pie-chart and Bar Diagram. By conducting this study, it has been revealed by the researcher that customers in a greater majority were aware of Cloud Kitchens. The researcher has pointed out a need to effectively communicate the marketing of Cloud Kitchens in particular through Social Media Network along with its clear benefits.

Statement of the Problem:

The food and beverage industry has great impact on the environment and leaves an ecological footprint due to the high demand and a growing population. Current patterns of global consumption are unsustainable. Consumers’ lifestyles, including how consumers choose and use products and services have been changed. Consumer behaviour contributes significantly to the impact on the environment. At this present business world food industry has different varieties of outlets in the battle field facing stiff competition. Even cloud kitchens also facing a stiff competition since, it is established in 2015 and gained popularity in the wake of pandemic 2019 as they are set up to provide food exclusively for delivery. At this juncture it is important to identify the buying behaviour of the consumers towards cloud kitchen and also to cope up with the factors that influencing customer satisfaction towards the cloud kitchen. The main problem of the study is to analyse the consumer buying behaviour towards cloud kitchens.

Objectives of the study:

- To analyse the demographic profile of the respondents.
- To understand the awareness level of consumers about the cloud kitchen.
- To study the factors influencing the buying behavior of consumers perception towards cloud kitchen.
- To examine the problem faced by purchase of cloud kitchen

Research methodology:

The study adopts a descriptive research methodology to identify and analyse the research problem using appropriate tools and techniques. It is based on both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire, while secondary data were gathered from journals, magazines, and relevant websites. A

convenience sampling technique was employed to select 100 respondents for the study. The research was confined to the Coimbatore area and conducted during the period from November 2025 to January 2026, and the collected data were analysed using suitable statistical tools like Simple Percentage analysis, Friedman ranking analysis, and Average score.

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

**TABLE NO: 1
 PERSONAL FACTORS OF THE RESPONDENTS**

Particulars	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	58	58
	Female	42	42
Age	18–30	53	53
	31–40	23	23
	41–50	19	19
	Above 50	5	5
Occupation	Self-employed	21	21
	Professional	23	23
	Government employee	29	29
	Private employee	19	19
	Others	8	8
Educational Status	No formal education	3	3
	School level	18	18
	Undergraduate	37	37
	Postgraduate	21	21
	Professional	17	17
	Diploma	4	4
Family Income (₹)	Up to 20,000	18	18
	20,001–30,000	10	10
	30,001–40,000	24	24
	40,001–50,000	22	22
	Above 50,000	26	26
Marital Status	Single	47	47
	Married	47	47
	Divorced	6	6

Type of Family	Nuclear family	54	54
	Joint family	46	46
Size of Family	2 members	4	4
	3 members	25	25
	4 members	44	44
	Above 4	27	27
Residential Area	Rural	30	30
	Urban	61	61
	Semi-urban	9	9

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The table shows that the majority of the respondents are male (58%). Most of the respondents have aged between 18 to 30 years (53%). Most of the respondents have completed Under graduation (37%). The majority of the

respondents are the type of nuclear family (54%). Most of the respondents have 4 members in their family (44%). Most of the respondents had their occupational status as Student (29%) and their earning as monthly family income Above 50000 (26%)

TABLE NO: 2
SOURCE OF AWARENESS ABOUT THE CLOUD KITCHEN

S. No	Awareness	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Friends	22	22
2	Relatives	33	33
3	Advertisements	28	28
4	Websites / internet	17	17
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The above mentioned Table No 2 shows that 22% of the total number of respondents taken for this study were awareness thorough friends, 33% of the respondents were awareness thorough relatives, 28% of the participants were awareness thorough advertisement, 17% of the respondents was awareness thorough websites/internet. The majority (33%) of the respondents were awareness thorough relatives.

CHART NO: 1
SOURCE OF AWARENESS ABOUT THE

CLOUD KITCHEN

TABLE NO: 3
FACTORS INFLUENCED TO PURCHASE CLOUD KITCHEN

S. No	Factor influencing	Mean rank	Rank
1	Price	4.49	5
2	Hygiene	4.10	1
3	Menu variety	4.88	8
4	Taste	4.73	7
5	Quick service	5.0	10
6	Quality of food	4.43	4
7	Delivery fees	4.65	6
8	Convenience	4.30	3
9	Discounts	4.21	2
10	Preference of consumers	4.96	9

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table, it can be inferred the factors affecting consumers' choice of the cloud kitchen with their respective mean ranks. Hygiene stood first with the greatest mean rank of 5.0. Discounts secured second place with a mean rank of 4.96. Apart from this, convenience ranked third with a

relatively low mean rank of 4.30. However, the factors of food quality ranked fourth with a relatively low mean rank of 4.43. On the other hand, factors such as prices, delivery charges, and taste of the food ranked relatively moderate. In addition to this, variety and quick service of the food ranked the lowest.

PROBLEM FACED BY PURCHASE OF CLOUD KITCHEN
TABLE NO: 4

S.no	Problem faced	Level	Very true for me	True for me	Neutral	Very untrue for me	Very untrue for me	Total	Mean
		Score	5	4	3	2	1		
1	Difficult to reach customers	No	37	20	24	9	10	100	3.65
		Score	185	80	72	18	10	365	
2	Limited choice	No	16	36	28	14	23	100	3.51
		Score	89	144	84	28	55	351	
3	Lack of awareness	No	15	23	33	16	34	100	3.11
		Score	75	92	99	32	10	311	
4	Non - availability of dine in	No	16	19	33	26	6	100	2.75
		Score	80	38	99	52	6	275	

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The following table highlights the issues being faced by consumers regarding cloud kitchens on a

five-point Likert scale. The major problem being faced regarding reaching the consumers has shown the highest mean, i.e., 3.65, agreeing on major

issues, which need addresses. Limited choice, the second major problem being faced, has shown the second-highest mean, i.e., 3.51, agreeing on the issues being dealt less. Limited awareness has shown an average score, i.e., 3.11, indicating an urgent need to promote cloud kitchens. Limited facilities, i.e., non-availability of dine-in facilities, had the lowest mean, i.e., 2.75, indicating consumers are not considering it as a major problem. This suggests that the major problem cloud kitchen faces is being promotable to consumers.

Suggestion:

The cloud kitchen has some strengths and opportunities, which are positive aspects, but on the other hand, the cloud kitchen has weaknesses and threats in the market. However, these threats and weaknesses are not big hurdles for a cloud kitchen because these weaknesses and threats can be converted into strengths and opportunities through observation of customer behaviour, expectations, and food culture properly through customer feedback. More than half the respondents knew the Cloud Kitchen name before this research, and it is a very positive sign because people are a little bit familiar with this kind of restaurant. They have to know the food preferences of the customers, their expectations, and need to gain the trust of customers; then they can start their own food delivery. That's how they can save money and put more focus on the food. They also need to start cooking food on demand, like for birthday parties, marriage ceremonies, etc. Cloud kitchen food is supposed to be delivered as soon as possible and should have a rapport between the food delivery applications or should have their own food delivery applications.

Conclusion:

The research conducted on consumer behavior in regard to cloud kitchens in Coimbatore concludes that such types of restaurants are growing in popularity, especially among the younger population who are more interested in accessibility and convenience. Demographic variables such as age, education, income, and size and type of household have been found to impact consumer behavior and consumption choices. Knowledge about cloud kitchens is disseminated through relatives, friends, and advertisements, which

emphasizes the significance and significance of proper promotion and marketing. Consumer satisfaction is primarily based on star ratings, packaging, and cleanliness, which shows that quality is an essential aspect to be considered in building and maintaining customer loyalty and support. The results indicate that such cloud kitchen restaurants should have a strong emphasis on customer satisfaction regarding food quality, delivery, and customer service. Information about customer expectations and feedback may also come in handy in catering to such demands and expectations by customizing menus and programs accordingly. Improved internet presence and catering to customer demands regarding delivery can further improve customer satisfaction and support.

Reference:

1. Dr. Deepali & K. J. Somaiya (2024) Opportunities and challenges for cloud kitchen owners. *International research journal on advanced engineering and management*.
2. Rafiuddin Ahmed & Maria Sultana (2024) Investigating the factors that drive the success of cloud kitchen in Bangladesh. *Journal of islamic economic laws*.
3. Mr. Donald James & Dr. Anil kumar (2023): Evaluate customer awareness of cloud kitchen in Mangalore city. *International research journal of modernization in engineering technology and study*.
4. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381589961_ONDC_Opportunities_and_Challenges_for_Cloud_Kitchen_Owners
5. <https://journals2.ums.ac.id/index.php/jisel/article/view/5295>
6. <https://ijsart.com/public/storage/paper/pdf/IJSARTV10I590900>